

MECHANISM OF THE MICROBIOLOGICAL OXIDATION OF AMMONIA. PART II.

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The inhibitory action of capillary active substances like urethanes, nitriles, alcohols and ketones on the microbiological oxidation of ammonia has been studied by following Erlenmeyer's technique. The action of cyanides has also been studied. These substances have been found to inhibit the respiration of the bacteria for some time after which, however, nitrite begins to appear, the period of inhibition is found to increase generally with the increase in concentration of the narcotic. These experiments lead to the conclusion that the oxidation of ammonia is a surface catalytic reaction taking place at certain active centres on the surface of the bacteria.

In a previous publication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **14**, 598) the question of the formation of intermediate products in the microbiological oxidation of ammonia was discussed. Our experiments showed that hydroxylamine and hyponitrite could not be detected in the process of oxidation of ammonia to nitrite.

To elucidate the mechanism of oxidation of ammonia by the bacteria we have studied the action of capillary active substances like the alcohols, the ketones and the nitriles and that of specific narcotics like potassium cyanide and hydrocyanic acid on the course of this oxidation. Meyerhof used the familiar Barcroft manometer technique for a similar study, but we made a new departure, in that we used the Erlenmeyer technique. In the first method Meyerhof followed the course of the reaction only during a small interval of time by noting the absorption of oxygen in the manometer. On the other hand, following the Erlenmeyer's technique we observed the reaction for a long period of several days, estimating the concentration of nitrite formed at intervals. Very interesting results have been obtained, which are recorded in the following pages.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The method of culture of the bacteria was the same as described in Part I.

Effect of Potassium Cyanide.—100 ml portions of the culture medium were introduced into sterilised Erlenmeyer flasks (500 ml.) and 1 g. of magnesium carbonate was added to each flask. The enriched culture (1 ml.) of the nitrite forming bacteria was pipetted by means of a sterile pipette into these flasks. Varying volumes of potassium cyanide solution were

then measured out into these flasks to give different concentrations. The total volume in each flask was made up to 200 ml. by the addition of the requisite quantity of sterile distilled water. The flasks were plugged with sterile cotton and incubated at 30°.

The amount of nitrite nitrogen in mg. per litre in each flask was estimated from time to time and the following table shows the results obtained. Figures in the tables refer to mg. of nitrite-nitrogen per litre.

TABLE I.

Influence of potassium cyanide.

Incubated for	Concentration of potassium cyanide					
	Nil. (Control.)	M/40,000.	M/4,000.	M/1,000.	M/250.	M/50.
0 days	2.4	2.0	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.0
18	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.8
30	4.5	2.0	2.4	2.2	2.2	2.4
41	23.3	2.2	2.2	2.1	2.3	2.2
46	41.2	2.1	2.2	2.1	2.3	2.2
54	82.9	2.3	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.1
62	112.0	6.9	3.0	2.3	2.2	2.1
69	164.0	28.0	8.0	2.6	2.5	2.2
76	—	70.9	36.8	3.3	3.3	2.2
88	—	112.0	52.8	44.4	5.1	2.4
99	—	—	80.0	50.0	26.2	2.0
107	—	—	—	65.9	40.0	2.0

TABLE II.

Influence of hydrocyanic acid.

Incubated for	Concentration of hydrocyanic acid.				
	Nil. (Control.)	M/40,000.	M/10,000.	M/2,500.	M/500.
0 days	2.4	2.0	2.0	2.2	2.0
18	2.2	2.0	2.2	2.2	2.0
30	4.5	2.1	2.4	2.5	2.4
41	23.3	2.2	2.3	2.6	2.3
46	41.2	2.2	2.4	2.6	2.5
54	82.9	2.4	2.4	2.5	2.5
62	112.0	3.4	4.2	3.9	2.4
69	164.0	19.5	19.5	23.1	2.8
76	—	52.8	56.0	57.4	5.3
88	—	97.5	88.2	114.2	22.4
99	—	—	—	—	46.7
107	—	—	—	—	59.4

From the above two tables it appears that cyanides inhibit the growth and respiration of nitrite forming bacteria even at as low a concentration as $M/40,000$. In the control flask nitrite begins to form in thirty days after inoculation and steadily increases thereafter, while in the flasks containing cyanide, nitrite begins to form only after a long incubation period, the minimum period being about 62 days. The length of this period increases with increasing concentration of the cyanide. Cyanide appears to be destroyed during this inhibition and when the cyanide disappears completely, the growth and respiration of the bacteria begins leading to the formation of nitrite. A steady increase in the amount of nitrite formed is observed from this time.

A very interesting point emerges from this investigation. Even in these flasks, where the concentration of potassium cyanide is initially as high as $M/50$, the growth and respiration of bacteria begins and progresses as evidenced by the increasing accumulation of nitrite, though this happens after a long time. This shows that this narcotic effect of cyanide is reversible; the cyanide does not permanently kill the bacteria but exerts only a temporary inhibition on the respiration. During the long period of inhibition the cyanide disappears and then the respiration and growth of bacteria start. In the presence of cyanide, the bacteria are in some sort of quiescent state but are not killed. It would be an interesting work for bacteriologists to define exactly what this quiescent inactive state is. We express the hope that these results may be of considerable importance in connection with the poisonous action of cyanides on higher animals.

Gopala Rao and Pandalai (*Archiv Mikrobiol.*, 1936, 7, 32) obtained similar results with potassium ferrocyanide and ferricyanide. They found that the narcotic effect can be demonstrated even in actively growing cultures. Now we have found that the appearance of nitrite after a long time in flasks to which cyanide was added at the start is not due to the bacteria getting acclimatised to the narcotic; for if cyanide is again added after a considerable accumulation of nitrite takes place, the respiration of the bacteria is again inhibited. This was confirmed in another way. Inoculations from cultures grown in presence of cyanide were made into fresh media containing cyanide in order to study whether bacteria, which remained inactive in the presence of cyanide for a long time and later resumed normal activity, can resist the action of fresh amounts of the poison. These experiments showed that such cultures were as much inhibited by the fresh cyanide as any other, while they are capable of growing and forming nitrite in a medium free from cyanide.

Effect of Capillary Active Substances.—In the following tables the effect of different capillary active substances were studied in the same manner as in the case of potassium cyanide.

TABLE III.

Influence of methylurethane.

Concentration of methylurethane.

Incubated for	Nil. (Control.)	M/10.	M/20.	M/50.
9 days	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.2
15	3.7	2.1	2.1	2.1
22	22.9	2.1	2.0	2.1
30	40.0	2.0	2.1	2.9
37	97.4	2.0	2.0	2.2
42	112.0	2.2	2.0	2.0
58	156.5	2.0	2.1	2.3
69	172.3	2.0	2.1	2.3

TABLE IV.

Influence of phenylurethane.

Concentration of phenylurethane.

Incubated for	Nil. (Control.)	M/500.	M/1,000.	M/2,000.
9 days	2.3	2.0	2.3	2.3
15	3.7	2.0	2.3	2.6
22	22.9	1.9	2.1	3.4
30	40.0	1.9	2.1	8.0
37	97.4	2.1	2.1	10.0
58	156.5	2.0	2.3	19.5
69	172.3	2.1	2.3	51.6

TABLE V.

Influence of acetonitrile.

Concentration of acetonitrile.

Incubated for	Nil. (Control.)	M/50.	M/100.	M/500.	M/1,000.
10 days	1.8	1.9	1.8	1.9	1.9
16	2.3	1.9	1.9	2.0	2.0
23	3.0	1.9	2.0	2.2	2.5
30	19.1	1.9	2.0	2.0	5.9
37	31.6	2.1	2.1	2.4	9.4
42	46.3	2.0	2.0	2.4	41.8
58	70.0	2.0	2.0	3.2	103.0
69	102.6	2.0	2.0	21.2	110.0

TABLE VI.

Influence of propionitrile.

Concentration of propionitrile.

Incubated for	Nil. (Control.)	M/100.	M/500.	M/1,000.
10 days	1.8	1.9	1.9	1.8
16	2.3	1.9	1.9	1.8
23	3.0	2.1	2.0	2.1
30	19.1	2.1	2.0	2.1
37	31.6	2.2	2.1	3.4
42	46.3	2.0	2.0	4.2
58	70.0	2.0	2.0	32.9
69	102.6	2.3	2.2	80.0

TABLE VII.

Influence of butyronitrile.

Concentration of butyronitrile.

Incubated for	Nil. (Control.)	M/1,000.	M/5,000.	M/10,000.
0 days	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8
23	4.9	1.8	38.8	46.6
29	25.5	6.0	83.6	82.9
36	39.4	28.0	113.0	100.0
43	72.8	37.3	118.0	154.0
52	118.0	112.0	195.0	105.0

TABLE VIII.

Influence of benzonitrile.

Concentration of benzonitrile.

Incubated for	Nil. (Control.)	M/500.	M/1,000.	M/5,000.
0 days	1.8	1.8	1.9	1.8
16	2.3	1.8	6.4	3.0
23	3.0	20.0	22.0	10.7
30	19.1	33.5	36.6	27.1
37	31.6	94.0	96.5	67.5

It has been found that there is an acceleration even at a concentration of $M/10,000$ benzonitrile. Previously, Gopala Rao and Pandalai (*loc. cit.*) observed that benzonitrile markedly inhibits respiration and growth of the bacteria at concentrations ranging from $M/10$ to $M/100$.

TABLE IX.

Influence of methyl alcohol.

Incubated for	Nil. Control. (1)	Concentration of methyl alcohol.				Nil. Control. (2)
		M/10.	M/20.	M/40.	M/100.	
0 days.	2.3	2.0	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.3
12	3.6	—	—	—	—	4.5
19	9.7	—	—	—	—	10.9
26	32.9	—	—	—	7.5	27.6
35	43.1	—	2.2	—	—	48.7
46	115.4	5.3	11.2	5.3	47.3	107.9
58	130.2	24.3	21.1	22.8	101.8	—
64	—	35	43.1	42.4	—	—
84	—	—	78.3	80	—	—

TABLE X.

Influence of ethyl alcohol.

Incubated for	Concentration of ethyl alcohol.				Nil. Control.
	M/10.	M/20.	M/40.	M/100.	
0 days	—	—	—	—	2.7
12	—	—	—	—	4.5
19	—	—	—	—	10.9
26	—	—	—	—	27.6
35	—	—	—	—	48.7
46	—	—	—	—	107.9
58	—	—	4.9	4.0	—
64	—	4.0	22.4	23.5	—
84	2.4	50.0	50.0	74.7	—
99	41.5	74.7	74.7	93.8	149.3

TABLE XI.

Influence of octyl alcohol.

Concentration of ethyl alcohol.

Incubated for	Nil. (Control.)	M/250.	M/500.	M/1,000.
0 days	2.7	1.9	2.1	1.9
12	4.5	2.1	2.3	2.1
19	10.9	1.9	2.3	1.6
26	27.6	2.2	2.0	—
35	42.7	2.2	—	—
46	107.9	2.4	—	—
58	—	1.9	—	—
64	—	1.9	—	—
84	—	1.8	0.7	0.5
99	149.3	1.7	19.8	30.6
108	—	1.5	25.2	45.2

It has been found that propyl alcohol at a concentration of *M*/250 slightly accelerates, while even at a concentration of *M*/50 there is no marked inhibition of the respiration (results not given).

TABLE XII.

Influence of acetone.

Concentration of acetone.

Incubated for	Nil. (Control.)	M/100.	M/50.	M/20.
0 days	2.3	2.2	2.0	2.0
7	3.5	3.2	2.8	2.6
23	15.1	23.3	14.0	3.1
33	46.6	46.6	25.0	6.2

TABLE XIII.

Influence of methyl ethyl ketone.

Concentration of methyl ethyl ketone.

Incubated for	Nil. (Control.)	M/500.	M/100.	M/50.
0 days	2.4	2.2	1.9	1.9
12	7.0	8.6	8.4	4.3
19	34.2	49.1	35.0	30.3
28	74.7	112.0	112.0	70.0

TABLE XIV.

Influence of methyl hexyl ketone.

Incubated for	Concentration of ketone.			
	Nil. (Control.)	M/1,000.	M/500.	M/100.
0 days	1.7	1.7	1.4	1.8
18	9.9	1.0	1.3	1.7
28	41.0	9.6	8.0	1.8
34	76.7	32.0	32.4	1.6
54	158.0	97.1	93.4	2.2

TABLE XV.

Influence of benzophenone.

Incubated for	Concentration of benzophenone.			
	Nil. (Control.)	M/4,000.	M/2,000.	M/1,000.
7 days	1.7	1.5	1.5	1.4
18	9.9	1.6	1.5	1.6
28	41.0	1.9	1.7	1.8
34	76.7	1.9	1.8	1.8
54	158.0	2.2	2.3	2.3
66	160.0	2.2	1.7	1.7

DISCUSSION.

Copala Rao and Pandalai have shown that it is unlikely that the biological oxidation of ammonia to nitrite by the nitrite forming bacteria involves a peroxidase-peroxide system. Pandalai (*Biochem. Z.*, 1939, **300**, 122) could not detect any dehydrogenase activity in the nitrite-forming bacteria.

Recent work of Quastel (*Biochem. J.*, 1926, **20**, 166), Quastel and Wooldridge (*ibid.*, 1927, **21**, 148, 1224; 1928, **22**, 689) and of others has shown that a suspension of bacteria behaves in a manner identical with any colloid system possessing catalytic properties and can be investigated precisely in the same way. The fact that a suspension of resting bacteria can be regarded in a manner similar to a catalytic system is indicated by its ability to bring about reversible reactions whose equilibrium points are independent of the amount and the conditions of the organism employed. Cook and Woolf (*Biochem. J.*, 1926, **20**, 545; 1928, **22**, 474) have demonstrated that the equilibrium point of the reversible formation of aspartic acid from fumaric acid and ammonia is the same with a number of different organisms and muscle tissue. The fact that dissimilar biological materials give the same equilibrium point is a good indication that truly catalytic systems are being investigated.

With some bacteria the range of activation seems to be very wide. *B. Coli* has been found to activate at least 56 substances so that they could reduce methylene blue in vacuum. A systematic study by Quastel of the effect of various selective poisons on *B. Coli* has revealed that the activation is associated with definite specially active patches; and that these patches have specificity or the power of discrimination between different substrates. The power of a given patch to adsorb different substrates depends on their chemical constitution, so that only a few substances are adsorbed; and of those substances which are adsorbed, only a small proportion is activated. The active patches on the cell surface vary in their capacity for activation considerably—some active centres will be capable of activating only certain types of molecules, while they are without action on other molecules. These experiments bring to light the close analogy of bacterial reactions in heterogeneous catalytic reactions occurring at the surface of metal or metal oxide catalysts. Much of the work on surface catalysis carried out within recent years has gone to show that catalytic activity occurs at particular active patches on the surface and that these active patches may vary in their capacity to adsorb reactants and activate them for chemical reaction.

Some bacteria may not have such a wide range of activation as is the case with *B. Coli*. They may be very highly specific and activate only one type of molecules. To this class belong the organisms that can bring about the oxidation of ammonia to nitrite. So far it has been found that only ammonia is activated by these bacteria.

It may be considered that as the cell grows the various synthetic processes culminating in the formation of proteins, etc., are such as to bring about the formation of active centres on the structures. The active patches are simply a property of the surface structures of the colloidal materials which make up the cell as a whole and is simply due to the conditions which obtain in the living cell, so that just that arrangement or juxtaposition of cellular material occurs with the formation of active centres. The centres may be regarded as points or regions of instability, places where a loose fitting of some of the molecules constituting the cellular aggregates occurs. The actual magnitude of the colloidal structures containing the centre is not of great significance. It would be expected that the smaller the structure, the less chance is there of its possessing a number of different centres, and hence of possessing an extensive range of activation. This may explain the exclusively specific nature of the nitrifying organisms—these organisms appear to be very elementary in their development, for they cannot utilise any of the complex organic molecules. They oxidise ammonia and the energy liberated in this exothermal reaction is partly utilised for their life

activities and partly for the chemosynthesis of carbohydrates from the carbon dioxide of the atmosphere. Other organisms of this type which are only capable of acting on inorganic metabolites such as the hydrogen bacteria, the nitrite oxidising bacteria, etc. are highly specific and act only on one substrate; whereas the more highly organised bacteria such as the *B. Coli*, the pneumococcus, the staphylococcus, etc. are not so exclusively specific but are active towards quite a large number of substrates. It appears that the higher an organism is placed in the scale of evolution, the wider the range of its activity.

The results presented in this paper show that the oxidation of ammonia occurs as a heterogenous catalytic reaction at the surface of the bacterial cells. The inhibitory action of urethanes, alcohols, etc. shows that the action is not specific and that the "poisons" simply act by competing with the substrate for the space available for adsorption at the active centres of cellular surface. The inhibition by these substances is marked only at sufficiently high concentrations. It will also be observed that in the same series of compounds, the concentration required for marked inhibition is lower in the case of a compound of a higher molecular weight than in the case of one of low molecular weight. Thus in the case of ethyl alcohol marked inhibition is obtained at a concentration of $M/10$, whereas with the octyl alcohol a similar result is obtained even at a concentration of $M/500$; acetone produces marked inhibition at $M/20$, methyl hexyl ketone at $M/100$ and benzophenone at $M/4,000$. These results could be explained on the supposition that adsorbability and inhibitory capacity run parallel to one another. It is well known from Traube's rule that in a homologous series adsorbability of a compound increases as the molecular weight is increased.

Curiously enough it is noticed that butyronitrile and benzonitrile at low concentrations of the order of $M/5,000$ — $M/1,000$ accelerate the reaction instead of retarding it; the inhibitory action of benzonitrile is manifest only at higher concentrations, say $M/100$.

While the inhibitory action of the urethanes, alcohols, ketones, etc. is manifest only at relatively high concentrations, potassium cyanide and hydrocyanic acid completely inhibit the growth and respiration of the bacteria at extremely low concentrations of the order of $M/40,000$. This result shows that activity of the centres is very likely due to a complex containing a heavy metal like iron. The cyanide acts by selectively poisoning these iron-rich centres.